

Sixteenth-century evidence regarding the origins of the Capeverdean verbal marker **-ba**

*Evidências seiscentistas sobre a origem do marcador verbal -ba
do kabuverdianu*

John Holm

Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal
jholm@mail.telepac.pt

Abstract: This article explores the possibility that some inflectional morphemes in modern creoles are not the result of recent decreolization but have existed in some restructured varieties of Portuguese used by Africans since the 16th century. It compares the anterior suffix *-ba* found on Sotavento Capeverdean verbs such as *kantaba* ‘cantava’ ‘was singing’ (cf. P *cantava*) with the corresponding Guinea-Bissau anterior marker *ba*, which is a free morpheme, a fact that led to speculation that both have a dual origin in Portuguese *-va* and a postverbal serial verb (*ka*)*ba* influenced by the substrate. However, what appears to be a past or anterior inflection *-ba* occurs in a passage in the Portuguese of Africans in a play written in 1524: the copula *sa* takes the suffix *-ba* and is translated as ‘era’ [‘was’]. The implications of the existence of this early occurrence of *saba* are then considered, along with the etymology of the copula *sa* or *sã* in archaic Portuguese and modern African and Asian varieties of creole Portuguese.

Keywords: Língua de Preto; Copula; Creole inflections.

Resumo: Este trabalho explora a hipótese segundo a qual morfemas flexionais em línguas crioulas modernas não são o resultado de crioulição recente posto que já estavam presentes em algumas variedades de português reestruturado empregadas por africanos desde o século XVI. Este artigo compara o sufixo anterior *-ba* encontrado em verbos do kabuverdianu de Sotavento

como em *kantaba* ‘cantava’ com o marcador correspondente do kriyol de Guiné-Bissau *ba*, um morfema livre, o que nos permite supor que ambos possuem uma origem dupla no português, ou seja, *-va* e no verbo serial pós-verbal (*ka*)*ba*, influenciados pelas línguas do substrato. Contudo, o que parece ser uma flexão de passado ou de anterior *-ba* ocorre na passagem do português supostamente falado por africanos em uma peça teatral escrita em 1524: a cópula *sa* recebe o sufixo *-ba* e pode ser traduzida como ‘era’. As implicações da existência desta ocorrência de *saba* são então consideradas, juntamente com a etimologia da cópula *sa* ou *sã* no português arcaico e nas variedades modernas dos crioulos de base portuguesa da África e da Ásia.

Palavras-chave: Língua de Preto; cópula; flexão.

1 Introduction

This paper offers newly uncovered evidence to help solve an old problem with important implications for linguistic theory: whether inflectional morphemes have existed in some restructured varieties of Portuguese used by Africans since the very beginnings of these varieties, rather than being the result of comparatively recent decreolization.

2 The morpheme (-)ba: bound or free?

One of the few indisputable inflections found in basilectal varieties of the Atlantic creoles is the past or anterior marker **-ba** found in Capeverdean (CV): *kantaba* ‘cantava’¹ (Lopes da Silva 1957:140). This “**-ba**...foi tirada dos verbos portugueses da 1^a conjugação (canta-va) e assumiu a forma **-ba**” (ibid.)²

However, the credibility of this etymology alone was undermined by the nearly total lack of inflected forms in other Atlantic creoles and the fact that in the closely related Portuguese-based creole of Guinea-Bissau (GB), the past/anterior marker **ba** is not a bound morpheme like its Capeverdean counterpart:

¹Was singing.

²**-ba** was taken from the first conjugation of Portuguese verbs (canta-va) and took the form **-ba**.

(1) GB (Kihm 1994:99)

N **konta u ba...**

1S tell 2S PAST

I told you...

Kihm suggests conflation with GB **kaba** ‘finish’ (cf. P *acabar* idem) and substrate forms: ‘...we may suppose that both /-**va**/ and (*a*)*cabar*, the latter reinforced by the phonetically similar Manjaku, Diola-Fogny, and perhaps still other languages, **ba**, had to enter into the process’ (1994: 103). Boretzky (1983:132) agrees that Im Crioulo von Guinea-Bissau ist *kaba zu ba* verkürzt worden, erscheint aber ebenfalls nach dem Verb und drückt Vorzeitigkeit aus³. As Jacobs (2012: 212) points out in reference to the Atlantic creoles, ‘...a postverbal past marker is not found in any creole other than So[toventó] CV and GBC (Kihm 1994:103), a circumstance that requires an explanation’, which may in fact be the dual origin of **ba** in Portuguese -**va** and a postverbal serial verb (**ka**)**ba**.

Baptista (2002: 201) pointed out that CV ‘...-**ba** is a verbal inflection found exclusively bound to verb stems’, causing speculation that the CV inflection -**ba** may have had its origin in a free morpheme like GB **ba** but later came to conform to the bound-morpheme status of the Portuguese inflection -**va** through decreolization. It has also been pointed out that Portuguese -**va** alone as the etymon of CV -**ba** and GB **ba** seems unlikely in that no other examples are known of creole morphemes being derived from superstrate inflections, which cannot be isolated or stressed and tend to be semantically opaque, thus not lending themselves to transfer.

3 Língua de Preto -ba

As the Portuguese sailed farther and farther south along the western coast of Africa in the 15th century until they rounded the Cape of Good Hope in 1488 and reached India in 1498, they established trading posts and began bringing Africans back to Portugal, first to be trained as interpreters for later voyages and then to work as slaves in Lisbon and on the large estates of the Algarve. Gil Vicente and other 16th century Portuguese dramatists created literary representations of the speech of these Africans, which came to be known as

³In the Creole of Guinea-Bissau **kaba** has been shortened to **ba** and also occurs after the verb to express anteriority.

língua de preto or *falar guinéu*. These texts have been studied by linguists such as Coelho (1880-86), Teyssier (1959, 2005) and Naro (1978). Naro claimed that the speech forms that arose between Africans and Portuguese in Europe represent a true pidgin which then served as a model for the Portuguese pidgin that emerged in Africa, but there is scant evidence that this *Língua de Preto* (LP) represents a stable pidgin with norms rather than simply the Portuguese of foreigners with errors that were not random only insofar as they were influenced by its speakers' first languages. These were apparently often related to the same languages, in fact, that were part of the substratum of some Portuguese pidgins and creoles, which accounts for certain of its similarities to these. The present study has identified a structure that throws light on the above controversy regarding the free or bound status of the morpheme **ba**: what appears to be a past or anterior inflection **-ba** occurs in a passage in *Língua de Preto* in a play called *O Negro da Frágua d'Amor*, written by Gil Vicente in 1524 (Teyssier 2005: 285):

	Língua de Preto	Portuguese
(2)	Oyae, seoro ferreyro, boso meu negro torna como mi saba primeyro!	Olhai, senhor ferreiro transformai-me vós em negro Como eu era primeiro

The form **sa** is clearly the LP copula **sa** (also spelled **saa**) as in:

(3) LP (Teyssier 2005)

Tu saa home o saa riabo?
2s COP man or COP devil
'Are you a man or a devil?'

Thus the only possible meaning of **saba** is past 'was', as the translation *era* indicates (See Section 4). While the relationship between the LP and the modern Upper Guinea creoles is not straightforward, this documentation of an apparently inflectional form **-ba** in the 16th century suggests that the bound status of modern CV **-ba** might not be the product of modern decreolization.

4 The copula **sa** in Creole Portuguese

Lipski (2002:66) points out that the copula **sa** occurs in three Gulf of Guinea creoles: São Tomé (ST), Principense (PR) and Annobón (AB):

- (4) ST (Ivens Ferraz 1979:77)

E sa pletu.

3s COP black

‘He is black.’

- (5) PR (Günther 1973: 85)

Ina sa migu mutu

3p COP friend very

‘They are very good friends.’

- (6) AB (Post 1995:199)

Xama Zwan sa?

place John COP

‘Where is John?’

Lipski (2002:66) also notes the alternate Annobonese form **sam** in Schuchardt (1888:196), but not the cognate form **tha** in Angolar (AN), in which the voiceless interdental fricative regularly corresponds to the voiceless alveolar fricative in the other Gulf of Guinea varieties of creole Portuguese. The former sound is spelled <th> (as in English) in Maurer (1995) and <T> in Lorenzino (1998):

- (7) AN (Maurer 1995:92, my translation)

Ê tha pisikadô.

3S COP fisherman

‘He is a fisherman.’

Among the Upper Guinea varieties of creole Portuguese, Lipski (2002: 67-8) notes the occurrence of a number of copular forms derived from Portuguese *ser*, but none with the form **sa**. However, such a form is indeed found in Cape Verdean CP:

(8) CV (Baptista 2002:86)

Dja korpu dja sa d'dade.

now body PERF is of+age

‘Now, I am old.’

The form **sa** in sentence (8) above is unambiguously a copula; it is not listed in Lang *et al.* (2002: 670), which does, however, list **sa** as a ‘part[icula] verbal, sempre seguida de **ta**, que exprime duratividade’⁴ Tavares (2012) also notes that CV **sa** can also function as a progressive marker: ‘...in Praia, although its occurrence is restricted, **sa** can stand alone with the same meaning and function of **sta** (and also occur without ta)...’:

(9) CV (Tavares 2012:58-9) (BT)

Pedru sta/sa fazi si trabadju di kaza.

Peter PROG (or FUT) do POSS.3SG work of house

‘Peter is doing his homework.’ or ‘Peter will do his homework.’

Of course the variation of **sa** occurring with or without a following **ta** to express progressive or habitual aspect is to be expected in a language that is still undergoing standardization. Tavares speculates that ‘...**sa** is a phonological variant of the marker **sta**...’ (2012:57), but it is interesting to note that Lang *et al.* (2002: 670) point out that **sa** has an allomorph **s’** and that the ‘confusão com o verbo **sta** encontra-se por vezes a grafia **sta** em vez do correcto s’ta’⁵. Of course the first element in the CV combination of verbal markers **sa ta** could also have been influenced by the old CP copula **sa**.

There is a connection between the copula **sa** and the progressive verbal marker **sa** in the Gulf of Guinea creoles as well. Ivens Ferraz (1979) notes that the São Tomé progressive aspect marker is **ska**/f**ka** or **sa ka**: ‘The particles **ska**/f**ka** are contracted forms of **sa ka**. **Sa** is the verb ‘to be’ and **ka** is the serial verb **ka** preceding the main verb in the aorist. **Sa** places the action in the present, and **ka** conveys the progressive sense’ (Ivens Ferraz 1979:82).

Finally, Lipski (2002: 67) notes that the copula **sa** and its variants **sã** and **são** (the last of which he calls ‘arcaizante’) occur in no Asian varieties of restructured Portuguese except the creole of Macau (MC):

⁴Verbal particle, always followed by **ta**, which expresses durativity.

⁵That its confusion with the verb **sta** sometimes stems from its being spelled **sta** rather than the correct spelling **s’ta**’.

(10) MC (Ferreira 1973:148)

vôs sã iou-sua amôr
 2s COP 1s.POSS love
 ‘You are my love.’

Thus the copula **sa** or **sã** belongs among the surprisingly few Atlantic features in Asian varieties of Creole Portuguese (Holm 2009).

What is the source of the creole Portuguese copula **sa**, which clearly existed as **sa** or **saa** in *Língua de Preto* in the 16th century, as seen in sentence (3) above? The Macau CP form **são** suggests an etymology in the third person plural present tense of *ser*, but that variant could have been the result of decreolization. Lipski (2002:81) notes that in archaic Portuguese, Latin *sum* ‘I am’ and *sunt* ‘they are’ both began occurring in the forms **som**, **sam**, or **sã**, and after the 15th century the nasalized vowels [ã] and [õ] both began to occur as the diphthong [ãõ]. Thus the CP form **sa** could have evolved from a denasalized form of archaic Portuguese *sã*. This scenario, which seems entirely possible, leaves only one aspect of CP **sa** unambiguously to the Africans: since so many West African substrate languages have phonemically distinct nasal versus oral vowels (Holm 2000:148-151), the denasalization of **sã** to **sa** could have been the input of either the super- or substrate languages or both. On the other hand, the extension of the single verbal form to all persons in both the singular and plural could only have been the contribution of the Africans. More importantly, there is (to my knowledge) no attestation in archaic Portuguese of the *Língua de Preto* past form **saba** as in (2), which is as unlikely to be the creation of adult native speakers of Portuguese as a form like *beed* for ‘was’ would be for adult native speakers of English: it must be an African creation.

5 The implications of LP *saba*

We now return to the issue of how speakers of substrate languages without inflections like the so-called Kwa group (a sub-family in the Niger-Congo phylum that played an important role in the development of many Atlantic creoles) could have dealt with the inflections of superstrate languages like Portuguese, Dutch, French and English. The old answer is that they didn’t: they found semantically similar free morphemes parallel to those in their mother tongues and transferred their grammatical meaning to the corresponding lexeme in the superstrate, e.g. (Holm 2000: 212):

(11) Yoruba

àwǎn ɔkùnrin yí
 they man this
 ‘these men’

(12) Príncipe CP

inɛ ɔmi sé
 they man this
 ‘these men’

However, this explanation does not work when we are dealing with the relatively small number of substrate languages that are inflected. Clements (1996:110-112) notes that Marathi, the substrate of the Indo-Portuguese of Korlai (KL), has a highly inflected verbal paradigm, which also occurs in Portuguese, e.g. *cantar* ‘to sing’, *cantou* ‘s/he sang’.

(13) KL (Clements 1996:111) **kata** ‘to sing’; **kato** ‘s/he sang’

However, inflectional systems in the superstrate and substrate do not have to coincide so closely for inflectional morphemes to survive in creoles. Kihm (1994:131) notes that ‘Plural marking is...the only inflectional morphology there is in [Guinea-Bissau] Kriyol.’ Based in part on the Portuguese plural **-s**, nouns denoting humans (or humanized animals) can take a plural **-s**:

(14) GB CP (Kihm 1994:132) **omi** ‘man’; **omis** ‘men’

There is no number agreement with adjectives or other modifiers in basilectal varieties, although this can occur in more decreolized lects. Could decreolization account for the plural **-s** on nouns as well? Incanha Intumbo, in a personal communication cited in Holm (2008:301), argues against this being the case, given the inflection’s regular occurrence in basilectal varieties. Support for the pluralizer’s early presence in GB CP can be found in the inflectional marking of plurality in its West Atlantic substrate/adstrate languages such as Balanta, which make a morphological distinction between the singular and plural forms of class-marking prefixes on nouns.

Thus we must not dismiss out of hand the possibility of finding inflectional morphemes in a creole - or for that matter, a pidgin (cf. Bakker 2002). Holm (1989:269) may have been too fastidious in rejecting the status of *Língua de Preto* as a true pidgin because it lacked norms; the copula **sa** and its

apparently inflected past form **saba** (which occurs, elsewhere, e.g. on p. 291 of Teyssier 2005) could themselves be considered such norms. However, neither must we forget Teyssier's caution: '...estes textos não são dados recolhidos no seguimento de inquéritos linguísticos, mas apenas fantasias imaginadas por um poeta'⁶. Yet he also realized how tempting these texts are:

Esta língua de preto procura, evidentemente, reproduzir, ou pelo menos evocar, o falar dos escravos negros que, em grande número, se encontravam em Portugal no tempo de Gil Vicente. Era a época, precisamente, em que se constituía o pidgin donde saíram os crioulos. Não se resiste à tentação de procurar, nos textos de Gil Vicente agora estudados, indicações sobre a formação dos crioulos portugueses.⁷

I think we should heed Teyssier's warnings, but not stop analysing these texts for the rare light they can cast on the otherwise undiscoverable process of linguistic restructuring which inspired the poet.

References

- Bakker, Peter. 2002. Pidgin inflectional morphology and its implications for Creole morphology. In G. Booij and J. van Marle, eds. *Yearbook of Morphology*, 3-33. Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Baptista, Marlyse. 2002. *The Syntax of Cape Verdean Creole: the Sotavento varieties*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- Boretzky, Norbert. 1983. *Kreolsprachen, Substrate und Sprachwandel*. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.
- Clements, J. Clancy. 1996. *The genesis of a language: the formation and development of Korlai Portuguese*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- Coelho, F. Adolpho. 1880-1886. Os dialectos românicos ou neolatinos na África, Ásia, e América. Boletim da Sociedade de Geographia de Lisboa.

⁶These texts are not data gathered from linguistic fieldwork, but just the imagined fantasies of a poet.

⁷Of course this Língua de Preto tries to reproduce or at least evoke the speech of the blacks who had come in great numbers to Portugal during the time of Gil Vicente. It was precisely the period of the formation of the pidgin from which the creoles would emerge. One feels an irresistible temptation to look for the traits of the Portuguese creoles in the current studies of Gil Vicente's texts.

Reprinted 1967 in Morais-Barbosa, J. (ed.) *Estudos Linguísticos Crioulos*. Lisbon: Academia Internacional de Cultura Portuguesa.

Ferreira, José Santos. 1973. *Qui-nova Chencho*. Macao: Missão do Padroado.

Günther, Wilfried. 1973. *Das portugiesische Kreolisch der Ilha do Príncipe*. Marburg an der Lahn: H. Jungraithmayr. Marburger Studien zur Afrika- und Asienkunde.

Holm, John. 1988-89. *Pidgins and Creoles*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Holm, John. 2000. *An introduction to pidgins and creoles*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Holm, John. 2008. Creolization and the fate of inflections. In T. Stolz, D. Bakker and R. S. Palomo (eds.) *Aspects of Language Contact: new theoretical, methodological and empirical findings with special focus on Romanicisation processes*. Berlin, New York: Mouton de Gruyter.

Holm, John. 2009. Atlantic features in Asian varieties of Creole Portuguese. *Journal of Portuguese Linguistics* 8 (2): 11-22.

Ivens Ferraz, L. 1979. *The Creole of São Tomé*. Johannesburg: Witwatersrand University Press.

Jacobs, Bart. 2012. *Origins of creole: the history of Papiamentu and its African ties*. Boston/Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.

Kihm, Alain. 1994. *Kriyol Syntax: the Portuguese-based Creole Language of Guinea-Bissau*. Amsterdam, Philadelphia: John Benjamins.

Lang, Jürgen et al. 2002. *Dicionário do Crioulo da Ilha de Santiago (Cabo Verde) com equivalentes de tradução em alemão e português*. Tübingen: Gunter Narr Verlag.

Lipski, John M. 2002. Génesis y evolución de la cópula en los criollos afroibéricos. In Y. Moñino and A. Schwegler (eds.) *Palenque, Cartagena y Afro-Caribe: historia y lengua*, 65-101. Tübingen: Max Niemeyer Verlag.

Lorenzino, Gerardo A. 1998. *The Angolar Creole Portuguese of São Tomé: its grammar and sociolinguistic history*. Munich/Newcastle: Lincom Europa.

Maurer, Philippe. 1995. *Langolar: un créole afro-portugais parlé à São Tomé*. Hamburg: Helmut Buske Verlag.

Naro, Anthony J. 1978. A study on the origins of pidginization. *Language* 54: 314-49.

Post, Marike. 1995. Fa d'Ambu. In J. Arends, P. Muysken, and N. Smith (eds.) *Pidgins and Creoles: an Introduction*, 191-204. Amsterdam, Philadelphia: John Benjamins.

Schuchardt, Hugo. 1888. Kreolische Studien. VII. Ueber das Negerportugiesische von Annobon. *Sitzungsberichte der kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Wien* 116: 193-226.

Tavares, Bernardino C. 2012. The verbal system of the Cape Verdean Creole of Tarrafal, Santiago: a semantic analysis of the tense, mood and aspect markers. LINCUM: EUROPA.

Teyssier, Paul. 1959. *La langue de Gil Vicente*. Paris: Klincksieck.

Teyssier, Paul. 2005. *A língua de Gil Vicente*. Lisbon: Imprensa Nacional-Casa da Moeda.

Recebido em: 22/08/2012

Aceito em: 28/12/2012
